

USE OF ICT IN LANGUAGE TEACHING DISCIPLINE AT UNIVERSITY

¹Yadgarova Guzal, ²Shakarova Feruza, ³Abdusalomova Fotima

^{1,2} Senior Lecturers at NUUZ

³Lecturer at NUUZ

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7982493>

Abstract. *In recent years, the trend towards the use of technology and its integration into the curriculum has gained great importance. In particular, the use of ICT as an audiovisual material in the classroom for teaching foreign languages is growing rapidly due to the growing attention to communicative methods, and it is clear that the use of information technology is a great help for language teachers in stimulating and promoting the mother tongue.*

Keywords: *information technology, computer, interactive learning, Internet, multimedia.*

Introduction

Information competence, which has become one of the main indicators of quality education, is one of the main conditions of modern education, and its formation directly depends on the vigorous activity of students in an open information and educational environment. Modern information and communication technologies allow creating unique didactic conditions for developing and streamlining individual educational trajectories in teaching language disciplines at a university.

The use of modern information technologies in the learning process makes it possible to intensify and improve the quality of teaching the Russian language (as a foreign language) and disciplines of the natural science cycle, increase the number and volume of training and monitoring programs presented to students by reducing the time for their development and implementation, develop interest in learning activities and diversify it. It should be noted that the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the educational process is an effective way to increase students' motivation to study academic disciplines. The use of a computer as a means of displaying clarity and supporting the learning process has a number of unique features, making it easier for students to perceive and understand lexical and grammatical material. At the same time, the computer allows you to clearly and unambiguously present elements of linguistic visibility, focus students' attention on certain important aspects of the topic by highlighting them with color, using auxiliary drawings, diagrams, including animated ones. The computer allows you to expand the possibilities of presenting and fixing educational material, to involve students in the course of the educational process, increasing the motivation for the process of obtaining new knowledge. The computer qualitatively changes the approach to monitoring classroom and independent work of students, while providing flexibility in managing the learning process and making it objective and accessible. (1)

The visibility of the presented material increases the degree of its assimilation, since the visual and auditory channels of students' perception of external information are involved. This problem is successfully solved using repeatedly tested and widely used multimedia technologies.

Research Methodology

Multimedia is a joint representation of textual, graphic, numerical and sound and video information. The graphical representation of the educational material allows students to focus on

the key points of the topic being studied, enables the teacher to increase their motivation and increase their interest in learning and memorizing new material, i.e. to implement the fundamental didactic principle of teaching - the principle of visibility.

So, for example, when studying the topic “Expression of object relations in simple and complex sentences. (Lexical topic: Personality and profession)”, a multimedia presentation is used. In the process of developing multimedia presentations, a number of problems were solved, related, in particular, to introducing a new one for students vocabulary and lexico-grammatical constructions. When studying the text "Choice of Profession", the classification of professions and their names are displayed on the monitor screen in Russian with simultaneous pronunciation by the announcer. The multimedia manual implements the possibility of repeated repetition of the text and individual phrases, which enables students to better understand the material presented and, if necessary, pronounce individual words and phrases. The multimedia manual contains several blocks of additional material that contributes to a more complete assimilation of educational material by students. The manual also contains control-training and control tests, a block of lexical and grammatical material, a block of Russian words and phrases in the “listen and repeat” format, self-test questions and links to recommended literature indicating the relevant sections and Internet sources. To provide students with the convenience of work, the multimedia presentation is equipped with an extensive system of hypertext links. The created electronic product contains other software modules. The use of modern teaching technologies in combination with multimedia materials adapted to the specifics of student learning, as well as educational resources that are freely available, can increase the motivation, level and quality of students' preparation when studying the practical course of the Russian language. A special role in the formation of motivation is played by the novelty and form of presentation of the information received by the student, as well as their inclusion in the search, creative activity.

The current stage of development of human society goes in parallel with the informatization of all spheres of its activity. This is reflected in the education system as well. Informatization provides for the mandatory use of computer technology in higher education, which requires increasing the information and computer literacy of students and teachers. Particularly productive is the joint activity of a teacher and a student in the study of a foreign language and, in particular, Russian as a foreign language (RFL).(2)

It should also be noted that one of the trends of the modern stage of informatization of education is the desire to integrate ICT hardware and software. Let us consider in more detail the use of ICT in the educational process in Russian as a foreign language (because in the Republic of Uzbekistan the subject Russian is studied as a foreign language in national groups of universities), which is inextricably linked with the improvement of its teaching methods.

At the initial stage of teaching students of national groups, the purpose of such an activity is the developed didactic system for the formation of work skills using ICT both in the Russian language and in the disciplines of the natural science cycle. The previously used work formula "student - teacher - book" was supplemented by the formula "student - teacher - computer", which acquired particular importance at the initial stage of training, when tasks are being formed "from simple to complex". Here, maximum visibility and convenience of work, the possibility of self-control, ensuring optimal mastering of the curriculum are important.

When teaching Russian as a foreign language, the capabilities of Microsoft Office 2010 are widely used, which allow you to create text, graphics and other materials that contribute to the visual and effective introduction and consolidation of new vocabulary and grammar.

The specialized training programs used at the initial stage of training students of national groups, such as, for example, "Russian Holidays", "Tretyakov Gallery", "Moscow", "Journey through St. Petersburg", "Pushkin and Navoi: Two Geniuses of Poetry" and others are focused on formation of linguistic and cultural competence.

An effective and efficient form of presenting new material are presentations made in Microsoft PowerPoint or Open Office.org Impress, which is as powerful as Microsoft PowerPoint and is its free alternative. Methodically correctly selected, structured and visually presented on the presentation slides educational material helps to increase the efficiency of perception and memorization of lexico-grammatical and other material.

We will try to systematize where and how it is advisable to use information technology in education, given that modern computers allow integrating texts, graphics, sound, animation, video clips, high-quality photographs, large enough volumes of full-screen video, the quality of which is not inferior to television, within one program:

1) when presenting new material - visualization of knowledge (demonstration - encyclopedic programs; Power Point presentation program);

2) consolidation of the material presented (training - a variety of training programs, practical work);

3) a system of control and verification (testing with assessment, control programs);

4) independent work of students (training programs such as "Tutor", encyclopedias, developing programs);

5) with the possibility of abandoning the class-lesson system: conducting integrated lessons according to the project method, the result of which will be the creation of Web pages, the holding of teleconferences, the use of modern Internet technologies;

6) training specific abilities of the student (attention, memory, thinking, etc.).

- Summarizing the above, we can conclude that the use of modern computer technology and information technology allows us to quite successfully solve the following problems:

- provide an individual learning path for students;
- provide visualization of educational information;
- provide real-time self-control over the degree and quality of assimilation of educational material;

- to increase the motivation of learning due to the novelty of working with modern computer technology and training programs.

Information technologies make it possible to significantly change the organization of the educational process, use the capabilities of computer technology and electronic teaching and control materials in order to build an individual learning path for students.

Conclusion

Using the capabilities of existing software, in particular Microsoft Power Point, allows you to create colorful and information-rich presentations that have ample opportunities for teaching students phonetics, vocabulary of the Russian language and comprehending grammar rules. The presentation of lexical and grammatical rules in the form of textual material, as well as tables and diagrams, contributes to an increase in the efficiency of assimilation of theoretical material, the

activation of mental activity, the development of logical and abstract thinking of students. It should also be noted that when using presentations, time losses are significantly reduced, for example, there is no need to write educational material on the board. When using training tests, the possibility of repeating the same test multiple times, the possibility of using textbooks and reference materials without limiting the time allotted for its implementation is realized. When performing a control-training test, the student can see the results of mastering the educational material in dynamics.

After analyzing the experience of using ICT in conducting training sessions in Russian (as a foreign language) and independent work of students, we can conclude that ICT accelerates the learning process, increases students' interest in the discipline being studied, improves the quality of mastering the material, makes it possible to individualize the learning process and provide an opportunity for objectivity of the assessment. The volume and quality of students' knowledge increases, the motivation for learning increases, the learning process becomes more clear and understandable.

REFERENCES

1. Slastenin, V.A. etc. Pedagogy: textbook. allowance for stud. higher ped. textbook manager / - M.: Academy, 2005.
2. Vladimirova, L.P. Modern information and communication and pedagogical technologies in education / - Access mode: www.relarn.ru/conf.
3. Polat E.S. New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system. - M., 2000.
4. Salaberry, The use of technology for second language learning and teaching: The Modern Language Journal, 85(1), 39-56. M. (2001).
5. Akhmedova M.Kh. Information technologies and their use in the learning process. Scientific journal of the Fergana state. University, 2019. No. 2 p.223-229.
6. Akhmedova M. The Use of Information Technologies for the Development of Foreign Language Speech of Student: Eurasian Scientific Herald www.geniusjournals.org Volume 7| April, 2022
7. Panfilova A.P., "Innovative pedagogical technologies", M.: "Assembly", 2009, p.37
8. Taramova, E.A. Problems and prospects for the use of ICT in higher education // Actual tasks of pedagogy: materials of the VI Intern. scientific conf. (Chita, January 2015). - Chita: Publishing house Young scientist, 2015. P. 156. [Electronic resource].
9. Kazakova, T.A. The use of information and communication technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language at a university // Linguistics and intercultural communication. 2015. - Issue No. 3 (17). - S. 78.
10. Robert, I.V. Modern information technologies in education / I.V. Robert.- M.: School-Press, 2004.